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Research Article

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ABSTRACT

A survey of microbial load of meat pie, a ready-to-eat(RTE) food, sold as street vended items as well as in fast food restaurants, was carried out. The focus was on the fillings and study areas were 2 local government areas of Ogun State., Nigeria. The mean microbial load on the fresh meat pie from all the locations ranged from 7×10^3 - 3×10^6 cfu/g. Using standard Bergey' s manual of Determinative Bacteriology, the bacteria isolated from the samples were *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, *Murdochella asaccharolytica*, *Peptococcus niger*, *Lautropia mirabilis*, *Pasteurella multocida*, *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, *Cardiobacterium hominis*, *Peptoniphilus asaccharolyticus*, *Rickettsiae spp*, *Enterococcus gallinarum*, *Micrococcus luteus*, *Aerococcus urinaehominis*, *Helicococcus pyogenes*, *Micrococcus lylae*, *Propionibacterium acnes*, *Neisseria polysaccharea*, *Streptococcus australis* . Using molecular methods, the fungal isolates were *Neurospora sitophila*-IMI 500339 ; *Aspergillus flavus*-IMI 500338 *Aspergillus niger*- IMI 500336 and *Fusarium solani* IMI 500333. The results of the study indicated that, all the meat pie samples studied in Remo L.G.A were heavily contaminated, rendering them unwholesome. Global best practices in food quality is hereby recommended throughout the value chain of the Nigerian food industry..

Keywords: Meat pie fillings, Ogun state, Nigeria, fungi, bacteria, microbial profile.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Ready to eat (RTE) foods can be described as food that was meant for immediate consumption at the point of sale. It could be raw or cooked, hot or chilled and can be consumed without further heat treatment (Tsang, 2002). Different terms have been used to describe such ready- to- eat foods: These include convenient, ready, instant and fast foods. Examples of such ready to eat foods include pastries, meat pie, sausage, rolls, burger, *moin-moin*, salad or coleslaw, fried meat, fried chicken, milk and milk products (Caserani and Kinston, 1974).

WHO, (2002) reported that food borne illnesses of microbial origin are a major health problem associated with street- foods as well as fast food centers and this is as a result of the traditional processing methods that are used in preparation, inappropriate holding temperatures and poor personal hygiene of food handlers which are some of the main causes of contamination of street-vended food. Consumers who depend on such foods are more interested in its convenience and usually pay little attention to its safety, quality, and hygiene (Mensah *et al.*, 2002, Muinde and Kuria, 2005; Barro *et al.*, 2006). Street foods are frequently associated with diarrhoea diseases which occur due to improper use of additives, the presence of pathogenic bacteria, environmental contaminants and disregard of good manufacturing practices (GMPs) and good hygiene practices (GHPs). Barro *et al.*, (2007) reported that vendors are often poorly educated, unlicensed, untrained in food hygiene and they work under crude unsanitary conditions with little or no knowledge about the causes of food borne disease. According to Doyle and Evans (1999), food borne diseases are diseases resulting from ingestion of bacteria, toxins and cells produced by microorganisms present in food. Data on issues of food borne diseases are well documented worldwide (Hazariwala *et al.*, 2002). Food borne illnesses is a major international health problem with consequent economic reduction (Duff *et al.*, 2003). Torok *et al.*(1997) recorded that outbreaks of food borne diseases are caused by those that are contaminated intrinsically or that become contaminated during harvesting, processing or preparation. In most countries, the most common food-borne illness is *Staphylococcus* food intoxication (Talaro and Talaro 1996). Enterotoxigenic *Staphylococcus* strains and *E. coli* strains have been isolated from foods implicated in illnesses (Adesiyun, 1995, Firstenberg and Sullivan, 1997; Cencil *et al*; 2003). *E. coli* and *S. aureus* are normal flora in human and animals, their presence in foods are indications of fecal contamination and excessive human handling (Adamolekun and

Adamolekun, 1992). The intensity of the signs and symptoms may vary with the amount of contaminated food ingested and susceptibility of the individuals to the toxin. *Escherichia coli* is commonly used as surrogate indicator, its presence in food generally indicate direct and indirect fecal contamination. It has been reported that in many countries of the world, there were lots of people who have suffered or even died from food poisoning arising from food spoilage especially young children (WHO, 2004). The need by the vendors to focus more on food hygiene as well as the regulatory agencies to ensure compliance with approved standard underscored the execution of this experiment

OBJECTIVES OF THE PROJECT

The aim and objectives of this study:

- To carry out a profile of the bacteria and fungi from meat pie obtained from different fast food centre in two local government areas of Remo Division of Ogun State.
- To suggest reasons for the comparative distribution of the isolated microbes in four investigated towns (Shagamu, Ilishan, Ikenne and Iperu).

2.1 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1.1 Study Area

The study areas are the standard eateries and local kiosk in four different places in Remo-L.G.A. Ogun state. The study areas were at the South western part of Nigeria, rain forest zone, with high humidity and temperature .

2.1.2 Collection of sample

Twenty - four samples each of meat pie were obtained from different fast food retail and vending centers at Iperu, Ilishan, Shagamu and Ikenne in Remo- L.G.A. Ogun state. The samples were immediately wrapped in sterile aluminum foil to prevent contamination and then transported to the Microbiology laboratory of the Bioscience and Biotechnology Department in Babcock University for microbial analysis.

2.2 Preparation and Inoculation of Samples

Each sample of the meat pie filling were removed, and mashed with a sterile mortar and pestle in the laboratory. 1 gram of the mashed filling was weighed and aseptically introduced into 9ml of sterile distilled water; this was properly shaken before 1ml was pipette from it into another test tube containing 9ml of distilled water until the last diluents was completed. Double plate of Nutrient Agar(BDH), Sabouraud Dextrose Agar(BDH) and Eosin Methylene Blue Agar were prepared and allowed to set before introducing 1ml of the sample of diluents from 10^{-3} and 10^{-6} into each Petri dish containing these medium. Incubation was carried out at 37°C for 24hours for bacteria growth and 25°C for 2-4 days for fungi growth. Colonies were counted in order to obtain the total viable count and coliform counts, discrete colonies were purified by sub-culturing into new prepared agar (NA, SDA) and growth was observed under the microscope and then characterized using standard method (Buchanan and Gibbon, 1994).

Total coliform counts:

The total coliform counts were performed using the spread plate method. Eosin Methylene Blue agar was used as a selective medium for the growth of the coliform bacteria. Plates were inoculated with 100 μl of 10^{-3} and 10^{-6} times diluted meat pie sample and incubated at 37°C . After 48 hours, the total numbers of colonies were counted with the use of digital colony counter.

Identification of isolates

Biochemical Tests for Identification of bacteria Isolates

Pure cultures of the bacteria isolates were subjected to various standard identification procedure and tests in accordance with the Bergey's Manual for Determinative Bacteriology.

Identification of fungal isolates:

All procedures were validated and processing undertaken in accordance with CABI's in-house methods as follows:

The original samples were subjected to a purity check. Samples found to be pure were processed using ITS rDNA sequencing analysis and, where stated in the sample report, also by partial calmodulin rDNA sequencing analysis. Molecular assays were carried out on the samples using nucleic acid as a template. A proprietary formulation [microLYSIS®-PLUS (MLP), Microzone, UK] was subjected to the rapid heating and cooling of a thermal cycler, to lyse cells and release deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA). Following DNA extraction, Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR) was employed to amplify copies of the partial ITS and calmodulin fragments of rDNA in vitro. The quality of the PCR product was assessed by undertaking gel electrophoresis. PCR purification step was carried out to remove unutilised dNTPs, primers, polymerase and other PCR mixture compounds and obtain a highly purified DNA template for sequencing. This procedure also allowed concentration of low yield amplicons. Sequencing reactions were undertaken using BigDye® Terminator v3.1 kit from Applied Biosystems (Life Technologies, UK) which utilises fluorescent labelling of the chain terminator ddNTPs, to permit sequencing. Removal of excess unincorporated dye terminators was carried out to ensure a problem-free electrophoresis of fluorescently labelled sequencing reaction products on the capillary array AB 3130 Genetic Analyzer (DS1) DyeEx™ 2.0 (Qiagen, UK) modules containing prehydrated gel-filtration resin were optimized for clean-up of sequencing reactions containing BigDye® terminators. Dye removal was followed by suspension of the purified products in highly deionised formamide Hi-Di™ (Life Technologies, UK) to prevent rapid sample evaporation and secondary structure formation. The samples were loaded onto the AB 3130 Genetic Analyzer and sequencing undertaken to determine the order of the nucleotide bases, adenine, guanine, cytosine, and thymine in the DNA oligonucleotide. Following sequencing, identification was undertaken by comparing the sequences obtained with those available at the European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL) database via the European Bioinformatics Institute (EBI).

3.0 RESULTS

The total colony forming units of the samples ranged between 7×10^3 – 3×10^6 cfu/g as presented in Table 1.

The bacteria isolated were *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, *Murdochella asaccharolytica*, *Peptococcus niger*, *Lautropia mirabilis*, *Pasteurella multocida*, *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, *Cardiobacterium hominis*, *Peptoniphilus asaccharolyticus*, *Rickettsiae spp*, *Enterococcus gallinarum*, *Micrococcus luteus*, *Aerococcus urinaehominis*, *Helcococcus pyogenes*, *Micrococcus lylae*, *Propionibacterium acnes*, *Neisseria polysaccharea*, *streptococcus australis* while the fungi isolated were *Aspergillus spp*, *Altenaria spp*, *Stachybotrys spp*, *Aspergillus tamari*, *Neurospora sitophila*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Aspergillus niger* and *Fusarium solani*.

Table 1: The mean for the total colony forming units (cfu/g) of bacteria isolated from the samples.

Sample	colony count	Number of Isolates
SGM	1.8×10^6	10
KNN	2.1×10^3	9
IPU	3.0×10^6	4
ILS	7.0×10^3	6

Each figure is an average of values from four replicates

KEYS:

SGM- Sagamu, KNN- Ikenne, IPU- Iperu, ILS- Ilishan.

Table 2: Gram reaction and biochemical characterization of the bacteria isolates.

Samples	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	Bacteria isolated
KNN 3B(1)	+	Coccus	+	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	<i>Staphylococcus epidermidis</i>
SGM 6(1)	+	Coccus	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	<i>Staphylococcus epidermidis</i>
SGM 6B (1)	+	Coccus	+	-	+	-	-	+	+	+	<i>Murdochiella asaccharolytica</i>
ILS 6D	+	Coccus	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	+	<i>Micrococcus luteus</i>
IPU 3B (PRO)	+	Coccus	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	<i>Murdochiella asaccharolytica</i>
SGM 6/3(1)	+	Coccus	+	-	+	-	-	-	+	-	<i>Peptococcus niger</i>
SGM 6B(2)	-	Coccus	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	<i>Lautropia mirabilis</i>
ILS 6B	+	Coccus	+	-	+	-	-	-	+	+	<i>Murdochiella asaccharolytica</i>
ILS 6C	+	Coccus	-	-	-	+	-	-	+	-	<i>Aerococcus urinaehominis</i>
SGM 6A	+	Coccus	+	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	<i>Staphylococcus epidermidis</i>
KNN 3C	+	Coccus	+	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	<i>Staphylococcus epidermidis</i>
KNN 6A	-	Rod	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	+	<i>Pasteurella multocida</i>
IPU 23	-	Coccus	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	+	<i>Neisseria polysaccharea</i>
KNN 3	+	Rod(bacillu)	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	+	<i>Propionibacterium acnes</i>
IPU 3(1)	+	Coccus	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	+	<i>Micrococcus lylae</i>
IPU 3(2)	+	Coccus	+	-	+	-	-	-	+	-	<i>Peptococcus niger</i>
KNN 6A	+	Coccus	-	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	<i>Helcococcus pyogenes</i>
ILS 6A	-	Coccus	+	+	+	-	-	-	+	-	<i>Peptococcus niger</i>
SGM 6B(3)	+	Coccus	-	-	+	-	-	+	-	-	<i>Streptococcus pneumoniae</i>
KNN 6C	+	Coccus	-	-	+	-	-	-	+	-	<i>Peptococcus niger</i>
SGM 3	-	Rod	-	+	-	-	+	-	-	+	<i>Cardiobacterium hominis</i>
KNN 3D	-	Coccus	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	+	<i>Peptoniphilus asaccharolyticus</i>
KNN 6B	+	Coccus	+	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	<i>Rickettsia</i>
SGM 3A	+	Coccus	+	-	+	-	-	-	-	+	<i>Staphylococcus epidermidis</i>
SGM 6(2)	+	Coccus	+	-	+	-	-	-	+	+	<i>Murdochiella asaccharolytica</i>
SGM 6/3(2)	-	Coccus	+	-	+	-	-	-	+	-	<i>Peptococcus niger</i>
KNN 3	-	Coccus	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	+	<i>Peptoniphilus asaccharolyticus</i>
ILS 3A	+	Coccus	-	-	+	-	-	-	+	+	<i>Enterococcus gallinarum</i>
ILS 3B	-	Coccus	-	-	+	+	+	-	+	+	<i>Streptococcus australis</i>

KEY:

A-GRAM STAIN, B-SHAPE, C-CATALASE, D-OXIDASE, E-CITRATE, F-COAGULASE
 G-STARCH HYDROLYSIS, H-UREASE, I-MOTILITY, J-INDOLE, POSITIVE: +, NEGATIVE: -

Table 3: List of fungi isolates

Samples	Names of organisms
A	<p><i>Aspergillus flavus</i> IMI 500338</p> <p>ITS sequence</p> <p>GGGTTCTAGCGAGCCCAACCTCCCACCCGTGTTTACTGTACCTTAGTTGCTTCGGCGGGCCCGCCATTC ATGGCCGCGGGGGCTCTCAGCCCCGGGCCCGCGCCCGCGGAGACACCACGAACTCTGTCTGATCTA GTGAAGTCTGAGTTGATTGTATCGCAATCAGTTAAACTTTCAACAATGGATCTCTTGGTTCCGGCATCGA TGAAGAACGCAGCGAAATGCGATAACTAGTGTGAATTGCAGAATTCCGTGAATCATCGAGTCTTTGAACG CACATTGCGCCCCCTGGTATTCCGGGGGGCATGCCTGTCCGAGCGTCATTGCTGCCCATCAAGCACGG CTTGTTGTTGGGTCGTCTCCCTC</p>
B	<p><i>Fusarium solani</i> IMI 500333</p> <p>ITS sequence:</p> <p>CCCTGTGAACATACCTATAACGTTGCCTCGGCGGGAACAGACGGCCCCGTAACACGGGCGGCCCGC CAGAGGACCCCTAACTCTGTTTCTATAATGTTTCTTCTGAGTAAACAAGCAAATAAATAAACTTTCAA CAACGGATCTCTTGGCTCTGGCATCGATGAAGAACGCAGCGAAATGCGATAAGTAATGTGAATTGCAGA ATTCAGTGAATCATCGAATCTTTGAACGCACATTGCGCCCCGCCAGTATTCTGGCGGGCATGCCTGTTG AGCGTCATTACAACCCTCAGGCCCGGGCCTGGCGTTGGGGATCGGCGGAAGCCCCCTGCGGGCAC AACGCCGTCCCCAAATACAGTGGCGGTCCCGCCGAGCTTCCATTGCGTAGTAGTAACACCTCGCAA CTGGAGAGCGGCGCGGCCACGCCGTA AACACCCAACTTCTGAATGTTGACCTCGAATCAGGTAGGAAT ACCCGCTGAACT</p>
C	<p><i>Aspergillus niger</i> IMI 500336</p> <p>ITS sequence</p> <p>CCGAGTGCGGGTCCTTTGGGCCcAACCTCCCATCCGTGTCTATTGTACCCTGTTGCTTCGGCGGGCC CGCCGCTTGTCCGCCCGCGGGGGGGCGCCTCTGCCCCCGGGCCCGTGCCCGCGGAGACCCCA ACACGAACACTGTCTGAAAGCGTGCACTGAGTTGATTGAATGCAATCAGTTAAACTTTCAACAATG D GATCTCTTGGTTCCGGCATCGATGAAGAACGCAGCGAAATGCGATAACTAATGTGAATTGCAGAATTCA GTGAATCATCGAGTCTTTGAACGCACATTGCGCCCCCTGGTATTCCGGGGGGCATGCCTGTCCGAGCG TCATTGCTGCCCTCAAGCCCGGCTTGTGTGTTGGGTGCGCGTCCCCCTCTCCGGGGGGACGGGCCCGA AAGGCAGCGGCGGCACCGCGTCCG</p> <p>ATCCTCGAGCGTATGGGGCTTTGTACATGCTCTGTAGGATTGGCCGCGCCTGCCGACGTTTTCCAAC CATTCTTTCCAGTTGACCTCGGATCAGGTAGGGATACCCGCTGAACT</p>
	<p><i>Neurospora sitophila</i> IMI 500339</p> <p>ITS sequence</p> <p>TACAGAGTTGCAAACTCCCACAAACCATCGCGAATCTTACCCGTACGGTTGCCTCGGCGCTGGCGGTC CGGAAAGGCCCTCGGGTCTCCCGGATCCTCGGGTCTCCCGCTCGCGGGAGGCTGCCCGCCGGAGTG CCGAAACTAACTCTTGATATTTTATGTCTCTCTGAGTAACTTTTAAATAAGTCAAACTTTCAACAACGG ATCTCTTGGTTCTGGCATCGATGAAGAACGCAGCGAAATGCGATAAGTAATGTGAATTGCAGAATTGAGT GAATCATCGAATCTTTGAACGCACATTGCGCTCGCCAGTATTCTGGCGAGCATGCCTGTTGAGCGTCA TTTCAACCATCAAGCTCTGCTTGCCTGGGGATCCGCGGCTGCCCGCGGTCCCTCAAAATCAGTGGCG GGCTCGCTAGTCACACCGAGCGTAGTAACTCTACATC</p>

Key=A: SGM 3, B: SGM 6, C: KNN 3, D: ILS
ILS 2(Ilishan)

The genus *Fusarium* is one of the most important fungi that include many pathogenic species, causing a wide range of plant diseases. The widespread distribution of *Fusarium* species may be attributed to the ability of these fungi to grow on a wide range of substrates and their efficient mechanisms for dispersal (Burgess, 1981). A number of *Fusarium* species produces mycotoxins that can contaminate a wide variety of crop plants; therefore, mycotoxins potentially could occur in a wide variety of feeds and foods (Nelson et al., 1994). *Fusarium* toxins are known member of Trichothecene mycotoxins that incite a range of lethal morbidities in man and livestock when consumed as contaminants with agricultural products. Another interesting role of *Fusarium* is the interaction with higher plants as endophytes (Pitt and Hocking, 1999; Munkvold and Desjardins, 1997). Among the most important diseases by *Fusarium* are ear and stalk rot of wheat (Zamanizadeh and Khorsandi, 1995), barley (Nejatsalari and Ershad, (1994), rice (Naeimi et al., 2002) and other economically important crops. certain strains of *Fusarium* species have been used in industry as biological control agents to control wide range of weeds, plant pests and diseases (Salleh, 2007). *Fusarium solani* (teleomorph *Haematonectria haematococca*; syn. *Nectria haematococca*) (Rossman et al., 1999) is a widely distributed soil-borne fungus pathogenic to many plant species. It causes wilt and rot diseases on a wide variety of crops including Cucurbita spp. (Hawthorne et al., 1992), *Pisum sativum* (Van Etten 1978) and *Phaseolus vulgaris* (Li et al., 1995).

A. niger became an industrially used organism when citric acid was first produced by fermentation in 1919. Citric acid is widely used in a variety of industries and by sales volume, it greatly exceeds other metabolites such as gluconic acid (Roukas 2000). *A. niger* is a rich source of enzymes. Pectinase, protease and amyloglucosidase were the first to be exploited, and were originally produced in surface culture (Frost and Moss 1987). Mycosis of the ear is one of the frequent health problems in the tropics. *A. niger* has been isolated from 5% of cases of chronic *otitis media* in Nigeria (Ibekwe and Okafor 1983). However, the authors consider the fungus to be a secondary invader rather than the causative organism because in most cases the patients had been treated with antibiotics before *A. niger* was isolated from their ears. *A. niger* can cause pulmonary infection (Binder et al. 1982; Denning. 1998). In rare cases it will invade existing pulmonary cavities and create a ball of matted hyphae known as aspergilloma. This aspergilloma may be present for years and may produce oxalic acid in situ, which may lead to renal problems caused by oxalosis (Nime and Hutchins. 1973; Severo et al. 1997).

Aspergillus flavus is saprophytic soil fungus that infects and contaminates pre-harvest and post-harvest seed crops with the carcinogenic secondary metabolite aflatoxin. The toxigenic strain of this mould is well reported in Nigeria and therefore a source of public health concern. In 1987, the International Agency for Research in Cancer IARC, an arm of the WHO, officially placed aflatoxin B1 on the list of Type 1 carcinogen. The implication of this is that this toxin is certainly causing cancer in man. The fungus is also an opportunistic animal and human pathogen causing aspergillosis diseases with incidence increasing in the immunocompromised population. *A. flavus* causes a broad spectrum of disease in humans, ranging from hypersensitivity reactions to invasive infections associated with angioinvasion. After *A. fumigatus*, *A. flavus* is the second leading cause of invasive and noninvasive aspergillosis (Denning, 1998; Morgan et al., 2005). The primary route of infection is inhalation of fungal spores. The bigger size of *A. flavus* spores (25 mm in diameter in comparison to 23 mm for *A. fumigatus*) favours their deposition in the upper respiratory tract. Possibly surface characteristics of the spores other than size are also important determinants of localization (Morrow, 1980). Most cases of cutaneous aspergillosis are caused by *A. flavus* (van Burik et al., 1998; Chakrabarti et al., 1998). *A. flavus* is a particularly important species in wound aspergillosis, accounting for 41 % of cases confirmed by culture (Pasqualotto and Denning, 2006). Many studies have linked the occurrence of postoperative aspergillosis with the dissemination of *Aspergillus* spores in the operating room (Pasqualotto and Denning, 2006). *A. flavus* is more likely to be recovered from the upper respiratory tract than any other *Aspergillus* species (Chakrabarti et al., 1992; Hussain et al., 1995; Iwen et al., 1997; Kennedy et al., 1997; Panda et al., 1998). Clinical presentations of *Aspergillus* rhinosinusitis include acute and chronic invasive, chronic granulomatous and noninvasive syndromes (Hope et al., 2005).

Neurospora is not a plant pathogen or plant pest. Burned or scorched vegetation is a natural substrate, but *Neurospora* has never been observed to invade living plant tissue or to cause disease in a plant. In 1989, an official of the U.S. Department of Agriculture Animal and Plant Health Inspection Service ruled that *Neurospora* species "are not subject to Federal Plant Pest Act regulations" (U. S. Department of Agriculture Animal and Plant Health Inspection Service PPQ Form 526, *Permit to Move Live Plant Pests*, no. 4432, issued by B. P. Singh to D. D. Perkins, 14 June 1989). Despite the many opportunities for human exposure to the powdery airborne conidia, no evidence has been obtained that *Neurospora* is the causal agent of any disease or infection. *Neurospora* does not appear from the medical literature to be a significant allergen. Medical textbooks on allergy either fail to mention or discuss *Neurospora*.

DISCUSSION

This surveillance step on the microbial load of meat pie fillings revealed the bioburden on this fast food. It should be noted that fungi were earlier detected as contaminants of some fast foods in Nigeria (Fapohunda and Ogundero, 1990). Detection of *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, *Peptococcus niger* and *Murdochiella asaccharolytica* in ready to eat (RTE) food (meat pie) was obvious in this study. Biological contaminant of bacterial origin presents a major cause of food-borne illnesses (Edema *et al.*, 2005). The presence of these organisms in ready to eat food (meat pie) depicts a deplorable state of hygienic and sanitary practices employed in the processing and packaging of these food products. From the results obtained, meat pie sample were contaminated with high level of *Peptococcus niger* and *Murdochiella saccharolytica*. From recent findings, bacterial contamination of food mixtures such as pastries, salads, sauces, and soups is not uncommon in inciting food poison outbreaks (FSRI, 2003; FDA, 2007 a, b, c, d). *Aspergillus species* are common moulds in soil and air and organic matter and are therefore ready contaminants of food and feed; it was therefore not surprising that the meat pie filling was a subject of invasion. The risk of vegetative colonization as well as the likelihood of mycotoxin secretion in the snack further raises alarm on the public health importance of the genus. Toxigenic *Aspergillus flavus* is recorded to cause Aflatoxicosis expressing as immunocompromise and liver cancer. *Aspergillus* occurs with increasing proliferation of the conidia in the human pulmonary region. The presence of *Neurospora sitophila*, a common mould on organic decaying or processed matter is suggestive of the hygienic state in which the fast foods were prepared and calls to attention the need to enforce safer standards by regulatory authorities, with particular reference to RTE foods. *Neurospora* species occur in areas of reduced level of hygiene and increased moisture. Using the colony count, the presence of *E. coli* is an indication of fecal contamination of the water source that was utilized in the processing of this food products (Edema *et al.*, 2001). This is an indication of possible recontamination in food handling hygiene techniques starting from the processing raw material to the finished product (Ikeme, 1990; Ojeibun, 1994). Some of the common fillings like minced meat are recorded to harbor large amount of microbial load (Phillips 2003). The EC standards of 10^3 cfu/g for most ready to eat food items was exceeded in almost all the sample areas (Table 1). From this investigation, it was observed that the issue of food poisoning is of paramount importance particularly in developing world where there are limited social amenities such as power and access to potable water. Food poisoning/illnesses are entirely preventable by practicing good sanitation and food handling techniques (Betty and Richard, 1994). Thus to safeguard against the risks of this disease of moderate severity as described by Mossel and Van (1990) on incidence of staphylococcal food poisoning, educating as well as advocating for good manufacturing practices among food processors is important. Hygienic conditions in terms of usage of aprons, handling of meat pie, use of contaminated water during washing, use of dirty processing utensils and covering of hair was not appropriately followed by the waiters and people in charge of the food preparation considered in the investigation. The fact that they are generally unaware of food regulation in Nigeria and have no training in food related matters, they need to be given urgent consideration.

Also relevant agencies in Nigeria such as Consumer protection Rights, NAFDAC and SON need to ensure and enforce strict compliance to Hazard Analysis Critical Control Points (HACCP) in all food production sectors in Nigeria.

CONCLUSION

Exposure during sale and before final consumption normally lead to the increase in microbial count. Because of the relatively high water content meat pie is best consumed immediately after production to avoid the rapid proliferation of bacteria,.. This may be attributed to non-enforcement of set standard of food quality by appropriate government agencies. Global microbial quality standard are expected to be maintained and enforced in all countries including Nigeria. Lack of appreciation of basic safety issues by vendors contribute to increase of the microbial loads. From the raw material handling, through water portability to final processing and packaging, the food vendor should be exposed to global best practices by designated institutions. Constant provision of relevant and current information, and the exposure to training programmes for food vendors and consumers, by approved bodies, will enhance the consumption of wholesome RTE foods including snacks like meat pie.

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